

Broiler AKIS mapping

Online Actor Map of the Broiler Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation system (AKIS) in each project country.

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List of Abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System
BIN	National Level Broiler Innovation Networks
BKH	BroilerNet Knowledge Hub
BNF	Broiler Network Facilitator
C,D&E	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
GP	Good Practice
GPET	Good Practice Evaluation Tool
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
PM	Project month
OG	Operational Group
TEN	Thematic Expert Networks

Executive summary

This deliverable report D1.1 is the first report of WP 1 Broiler Innovation networks on national and European level. WP1 sets the frame for all other WPs by establishing and facilitating national and European level multi-actor networks. The first step in establishing these networks is to identify the relevant Broiler AKIS actors (BroKIS) in each country to inform who should be involved in the BIN and whether this network can be built on existing networks. In each country a Participatory Actor Mapping (PAM) (Task 1.1) exercise was conducted in the period November 2022 to January 2023 to identify actors relevant to BroilerNet at the national and European levels and to create an understanding of who is involved in the sector.

This deliverable report (D1.1) present the methodology and provides an overview of the maps developed including the implications for the formation of the Broiler Innovation Network in each country. IN formation are discussed and recommendations made on how to take BIN and TEN formation forward.

The mapping exercise was first and foremost for the BroilerNet innovation network facilitators to get a thorough understanding of the sector in their country and inform the decision making on who to include in the BINs. Thereafter where possible these complex network maps were 'translated' and simplified and made available on the BroilerNet website to share our understanding of the broiler AKIS on national and European level.

1. Introduction

BroilerNet is a European thematic network project that will provide a platform for dialogue, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and sharing of innovative Good Practices (GPs) across Europe. The overall objective of BroilerNet is to enhance the resilience and the sustainability of the European broiler sector, by creating space for interaction between science and practice and co-creation of ready-to-use innovative best practices on broiler farms in Europe, at national and international levels. The project will engage with the most important AKIS (Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems) actors involved in the broiler sector within the 13 participating countries through establishing national level Broiler Innovation Networks (BINs). These national level networks will be connected on European level through three Thematic Innovation Network (TENs) in accordance with the three project thematic areas: environmental sustainability, animal welfare and animal health management. The BroilerNet Innovation Networks will ensure a bottom-up approach to identifying end-users/producers' needs in capturing ideas, practices and innovations from different knowledge sources, sharing of good practices on national and European level and in interaction with broiler-related EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs).

Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS)

The concept of Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) is used to describe how people and organisations join together to promote mutual learning, to generate, share, and use agriculture related knowledge and information. A great diversity of people are involved in creating agricultural knowledge. Farmers, farm

Knowledge and innovation play a crucial role in helping farmers, foresters and rural communities meet current and future challenges. To ensure that knowledge is shared between everyone who uses and produces it, and that people are connected, effective Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) are needed across Europe.

The first step in establishing these networks is to identify the relevant Broiler AKIS actors (BroKIS) in each country to inform who should be involved in the BIN and whether this network can be built on existing networks. In each country a Participatory Actor Mapping (PAM) (Task 1.1) exercise was conducted in the period November 2022 to January 2023 to identify actors relevant to BroilerNet at the national and European levels and to create an understanding of who is involved in the sector, their role, how they are linked and interact, their knowledge, interests and motivation, influence, available resources to engage, existing and potential alliances and conflicts, etc.

This task (T1.1) was first and foremost for the BroilerNet innovation network facilitators to get a thorough understanding of the sector in their country and inform the decision making on who to include in the BINs. Thereafter where possible these complex network maps were 'translated' and simplified and made available on the BroilerNet website to share our understanding of the broiler AKIS on national and European level.

This deliverable report (D1.1) presents the methodology and provides an overview of the maps developed including the implications for BIN formation. The actual information on each sector in each country and related BroKIS maps can be found on the BroilerNet website <https://broilernet.eu/news/national-bins/>.

2. Mapping Methodology

The network analysis tool adapted from Wielinga (2012)¹ as used as the core methodology for mapping of the BroKIS in each country. The exercise focusses on mapping out who should be involved in the BIN in each country, necessary connections (e.g., how are they linked) and identification of gaps and priorities for strengthening relationships. The network analysis focuses on the BIN in the centre and maps the BroKIS actors around it. The analysis provides insights to determine which actors should be involved, how they are linked and how influential they are, and whether there are any existing networks which we can engage with. This allowed each BIN facilitator to think strategically about who needs to be involved in the BIN and how they may (inter)act in the national network.

An online meeting was organised on 2 December 2022 from 10.30-11.30 CET to explain the methodology to the BIN facilitators. This was followed by an online workshop on 20 December 2022 from 9.30-12.00 CET to share initial results and provide support to the facilitators to carry out this

¹ H.E. Wielinga (2012): The Network Analysis www.toolsfornetworkers.nl LINK Consult, The Netherlands [https://www.linkconsult.nl/files/Modellen \(2014\)/Engels \(2014\)/NetworkAnalysis/120726_description_Network_Analysis.pdf](https://www.linkconsult.nl/files/Modellen%20(2014)/Engels%20(2014)/NetworkAnalysis/120726_description_Network_Analysis.pdf)

mapping exercise. The initial deadline for the report was set for 10 January 2023 and based on the request of the facilitators pushed to 15 January. As not all industry consortium partners had recruited or appointed the BIN facilitator yet this task was further delayed

The methodology consisted of 7 steps and the facilitators were requested to develop their map using PowerPoint or on paper and then transfer it to a Word or PowerPoint. The following guidelines were provided to the facilitators:

Step 1 Who are the BroKIS actors in your country?

Brainstorm and list all actors involved in the BroKIS in your country. There is diversity of actors involved in the sector: Poultry producers and/or representative organisations, poultry workers, integrators, public and independent private advisors, veterinarians, researchers, other relevant supply chain actors, input suppliers, retailers, media services etc. The more detail you can provide the better so not just '*private sector advisor*' but '*Happy Chicken Advisory services Ltd*' etc. Once you have exhausted your list go to your sheet and put your country name BIN and purpose of the BIN in the middle and map all the actors listed on your sheet by creating circles of equal size with their name and role written in the circle.

UK BroilerNet Innovation Network: co-creation and sharing of practice ready solutions to solve real day-to-day challenges of

Step 2: How are the actors connected?

Once, you mapped all actors on your sheet, identify how these actors are linked and connected to each other. Where the actors exchange something (information, services etc.), **add arrows** at the end of the line indicating the **flow of direction** of that exchange and indicate what is exchanged. Furthermore, visualise the **strength of the relationship** through **variation in the thickness** of the line between them e.g., a strong relationship has a wide line and very weak relationship a narrow or even a dotted line.

Step 3: How influential are they?

Furthermore, can you identify how much influence each actor has in the sector in your country. Influence can be formal or informal and source of influence diverse ranging from legitimate decision-making capacity to through giving advice or incentives. Adjust the **size of the circle** of each

stakeholder to illustrate **the level of influence**, increase the size if the stakeholders influence is high or reduce the size if influence is less.

Step 4: What capacity and motivation to working together?

The network map you have created provide initial insight into the actors involved in BroKIS in your country, their relationships and influence in the sector. Thinking of the BroilerNet project and its objectives what would be the motivation/ interest of each actor to engage with the project and their level of capacity in terms of time and other resources to engage with the project? Write next to all actors what their potential motivation would be to engage with the project, what would they want out of it? And, based on your own knowledge and experience can you rate the capacity of each actor by adding one to three stars (★★★ good ★★ sufficient ★ limited capacity)

Step 5 Are there actors or relationships missing?

You have created this map based on your own experiences and potentially with the help of your colleagues, to validate the map please ask **five** key actors in your sector to provide their comments and feedback. You can do this through sharing the map and inviting them for a short online workshop or to get their feedback through individual discussion by phone/zoom. Please choose any method that works best for you.

You can ask them:

- a. do you feel this map provides a good overview of the Broiler AKIS in your country?
- b. do you feel any actors are missing in this network map?
- c. are there any links (relationships) missing between actors?

List who you engaged with for the validation and revise your map based on the feedback of your key actors consulted.

Step 6 What are the implications for the establishment of your BIN?

Having done this network analysis, what do you perceive are the implications for the formation of your BIN?

- a. What do you perceive are the key actors who should be involved in terms of relevance to the project, their capacity and motivation, briefly indicate why?
- b. Are there any existing networks you could work with. If yes, what are the strength and challenges of working with this existing network
- c. Which actors could engage with the network based on specific knowledge needs?
- d. Do you foresee any challenges with the engagement of certain actors?

Step 7 Your BroKIS country report

Once you have worked through step 1 to 6, the only thing left to do is to write a short report including and elaborating on your map. Please write this report including the headings below

- 1 *Introduction and country context:* Please introduce the broiler sector in your country e.g., size, structure, importance, support, broiler meat consumption etc. etc. This context is important to understand and provide background to your network map.
2. *Overview and analysis of the (add country) BroKIS:* Present and elaborate on the network map, explaining the role of the actors, their most connection etc. This section should cover the information you collected in step 2 to 5.
3. *Implications for the formation of BroilerNet Innovation Network:* Referring to the map and the explanation provided in previous section elaborate on the implication for the formation of your BIN network in your country. This covers the analysis conducted in step 6.
4. *Way forward:* Please provide your conclusion in terms of who to engage with in your country and the potential intensity of engagement. Define who you will approach to form the BIN network in your country and why.

3. Results

In this section the results of the mapping of the BroKIS in each country are presented as developed by the project consortium industry partners. For each country the following is presented.

- *Introduction and country context*
- *Overview and analysis of the French BroKIS including the network map developed.*
- *Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Germany*

3.1 Finland BroKIS

Introduction and country context

Finnish poultry sector in general is rather small. There's been broiler production in the country since late 1950s, but the sector started to develop in the early 1970s.

The main parties in the Finnish broiler sector:

- *Producers and associations*

There are about 170 broiler meat producers in Finland and about 40 parent stock (pullet rearing and egg production) producers. Production is based on the production contracts and the industry is controlling the production amounts and setting the requirements for the production.

Broiler meat producers are private companies, usually run by families. The biggest farms have also employees working with the broilers.

Finnish broiler association was established in 1971 and most (more than 90 %) of the farms are members. Also, meat processors, feed companies and other broiler related companies, veterinarians and advisors are members of the association.

Finnish poultry association is the central organization and Broiler association [\(SIIPi\)](#) is a part of it.

- *Slaughterhouses / meat processors*

There's three companies, that slaughter and process broilers in Finland: Atria Oyj, HKScan Oyj and Naapurin Maaliskana Oy. The fourth one, Luomu Invest Oy, only process organic meat and buy the slaughter process from another company.

Meat companies have a major influence on the industry, for example they decide the production amounts and controls the production many ways.

Meat producers have a production contract with the companies or co-operatives behind the meat processors. Because of the history and location, producers nearly never change their contract partners.

The estimated broiler meat production amount in 2022 was about 140 million kilograms (81,5 million broilers).

- *Hatcheries and importers of day-old-chicks*

There are three animal import and hatching companies in Finland: Atria Oyj, DanHatch Finland Oy and Vilppulan Hybrid. The organic broiler chain is buying the hatching from a small private company.

Hatching companies talk closely with the meat processors about their needs for the coming years.

- *Feed companies*

Feed companies have advisory services for all farmers. Since the feed is one of the major production inputs and the most expensive one, feed companies have a big responsibility to maintain and develop the broiler industry. There are four broiler feed companies in Finland: A-Rehu Oy, Hankkija Oy and Satarehu Oy. Organic broiler feed manufacturer is RehuX Oy.

- *Research and development*

Since poultry production used to be a small business in Finland, research institutes have never invested in poultry or broiler research. University of Helsinki has the veterinary and agriculture faculty (including meat technology), but there is not much poultry related research.

Natural Research Institute Finland has some broiler related projects yearly and the broiler industry is always a partner in these projects.

SeAMK and HAMK are universities of applied studies and they are sometimes partners in practical projects like for example litter material trials.

Pyhäjärvi Institute is an expert organisation, that plans and implements development, research and further education projects in the food industry, water protection and the bioeconomy.

- *Authorities*

Ministries (Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry and Ministry of Environment) are responsible of legislation and connections to EU and EU countries and Finnish Food Authority executes legislations and controls laws together with Regional State Administrative Agencies.

Figure 1. Actors in the broiler sector in Finland and their relationships.

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Finland

Since Finnish Broiler Association (SIIPI) is a central and integrated organization for all operators in the broiler sector the BIN formation will be easy. Finnish broiler industry is small, and the actors described in BroKIS map are of interest to involve in the Broilernet project. A number of already existing working groups will make it relatively easy to recruit BIN members. From a farmer perspective, it would be preferable to include a mix of farmers from different areas of Finland, and that have different types of farms. Existing collaborations with the actors presented in the BroKIS map ensure that advisors, veterinarians and other experts can be recruited in a representative way. Thus, actor from e.g. abattoirs, hatcheries and feed companies can be mobilized to ensure a broad perspective on broiler framing. The sector magazine (Suomen Siipikarja) is published four times a year by the Finnish Poultry Association, and can be a good media for reaching the Finnish broiler sector for dissemination of project results.

The BNF 's ability and timing for of project management, as well as, the BIN actors' time schedules will be crucial for the partner engagement in BroilerNet. Using well-prepared instructions, time schedules and digital meeting tools as a compliment to physical meetings, the practical obstacle for collaborations can be mitigated.

3.2 France BroKIS

Introduction and country context

France is the 2nd chicken producer in the EU, behind Poland (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Share of quantity of EU poultry meat production (% , 2021)²

The French poultry, and therefore chicken, production and market are highly segmented, both in terms of species and production type (Figure 3 and Table 1). The latter can be summarized as follow:

- Standard : indoor, 39-42kg/m²,
- Standard +: reduced density (30-38kg/m²), feed specifications (French cereals, no GMO, flax seed...), enrichments, no antibiotics, ...
- Certified, which is gradually disappearing in favour of the ECC
- Free range:
- Traditional free range "Label Rouge": 2m² of outside available / broiler or total liberty with some other specifications on rearing length or breed used (varies upon brands). Can include protected designation of origin (AOP/AOC, ie "Poulet de Bresse")
- Agriculture Biologique: free range birds fed with organic feed.

Historically, there were four clearly defined chicken rearing types, with little variation from one brand to another. These past 10 to 15 years, each category has been segmented and new ones appeared as each company tried to differentiate itself from its competitors, such as: free range but not "label rouge" stamped, European chicken commitment and many improved welfare indoor bill of specifications. With the emergence of "welfare improved indoor" chickens, certified production has mostly disappeared.

Figure 3. Share of broiler chickens' production by production type⁵

² Eurostat, 2022. Agricultural production - livestock and meat
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?>

Table 1. Rearing specification by broiler production type

Production	Standard	Certified	Label Rouge	Organic
Breed	Fast growing	Intermediate	Slow growing	Slow growing
Age at slaughter	35-40d	56d min	81d min	81d min
Outdoor access	No	No	2m ² / bird or total liberty	4m ² / bird or total liberty
Barn size	No limit 1000-2000m ²	No limit 1000-2000m ²	400m ² max	480m ² max
Rearing density	39 (42) kg/m ² 20-25 birds	39 kg/m ² 18 birds	25 kg/m ² 11 birds	25 kg/m ² 10 birds
Feed	Depending on brand	65% min of cereals	75% min of cereals	95% organic ingredients No synthetic amino acid or coccidiostatic

Within each rearing systems, many species can be raised and slaughtered to fit a specific market (Table 2).

Table 2. French Poultry Sector diversity, % of heads slaughtered³

	2015	2020
Broiler	76.4	79.6
Capon	0.3	0.3

³ Anvol, 2022. Chiffres <https://interpro-anvol.fr/chiffres/>

Cull layers	3.6	3.9
Turkeys	4.5	4.3
Duck	3.9	3.4
Fat duck	3.7	3.4
Guinea fowl	2.5	2.3
Quail	3.8	2.8
Others	1.3	0.2

Despite being the second European producer and disposing of a wide range of products, France does not produce enough of broiler meat for its national market (4). French people eat 21.4kg of broiler on average (2019) of which 46 % was imported³. France does not need to import as much, however, import meat is often preferred, especially in the food service industry, as it is cheaper.

The French poultry industry counts about 15 000 companies³:

- 14 000 farms distributed as shown in Figure 5.
- 80 hatcheries
- 300 feed manufacturers
- 76 slaughterhouses
- 400 processing companies.

Figure 4. Evolution of production, exchange, and consumption of broiler chicken in France since 2000⁴

⁴ Agreste, 2022. *Statistical Book 2021 - Agriculture, forestry, fisheries and food industry*, Paris: DEJA LINK.

Figure 5. Distribution of broiler chickens flocks and location of main slaughterhouses in France⁵

Avian influenza (AI) has had an impact every year in France since 2006, with the first big crisis. In most recent years, AI has come back every year, with contamination cases mostly in the south-west of France. From August 2021 to May 2022, 1 378 cases hit French farms, forcing the cull of over 20 million birds⁶. Since August 2022, 287 cases have been confirmed on French farms. AI has spread to all poultry producing regions of France and is now endemic in the territory.

Inflation of raw materials and energy has been a concern for the past few months: the rising energy (electricity, gas and even wood) prices have been – and will be – challenging the profitability of broiler and all poultry farming.

Cost of life increase for the final consumer is also a concern: high quality products demand has dropped already, forcing organic and Label Rouge poultry producers to keep their barns empty for longer period.

Overview and analysis of the French BroKIS

The French broiler production sector is mainly integrated with production organization associated at least to its feed supplier, there are several actors involved in the Broiler Meat Supply Chain.

Figure 6 provides a good overview of the French broiler sector. There are too many actors to represent them all on this map. The main ones were named, but others had to be hidden for the map to keep it usable. As they are numerous, it is complicated to relate of all links between actors. Most

⁵ ITAVI, 2020. Filière volailles de chair. <https://www.itavi.asso.fr/page/filiere-volailles-de-chair>

⁶ Ministère de l'Agriculture et de la Souveraineté Alimentaire, 2023. *Influenza aviaire : la situation en France*. <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/influenza-aviaire-la-situation-en-france>

of them are connected by one way or another (selling/buying products, implementing law) The potential motivation and capacity of actors to participate in BroilerNet are still to check.

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in the France

Key actors who should be involved in relevance to the project are identified, but none were contacted to participate in BIN yet. Farmers of Terrena will be contacted more easily as Galliance (Terrena) participates in the BroilerNet Project. There are only informal networks among members of poultry farmers' organisations. Organisations might not all be cooperative; they are strongly independent, and the French broiler sector is competitive. Some farmers associations could be of help to reach directly farmers who are already in the "sharing state of mind", ie. <https://franceagritwittos.com/> on twitter.

Figure 6. Actors in the broiler sector in France and their relationships

Most influence

Medium influence

Capacity to work together

☆☆☆☆ Limited (mostly due to competition)

☆☆☆☆ Variable depending on partners and conditions

☆☆☆☆ Usually good

3.3 Germany BroKIS

Introduction and country context

Germany is the third largest producer of chicken meat in Europe after Poland and Great Britain⁷. Around 92,500,000 broilers are fattened on just under 4,000 farms⁸. This results in a gross own production of 1.04 million t of chicken meat for 2019.

A closer look at the slaughter figures shows that from 2010 to 2020 the amount of poultry meat produced increased significantly. Despite an overall decline in meat consumption, the popularity of poultry meat has been increasing in Germany for years⁹. In 2019, per capita consumption in Germany was 15.6 kg. However, this is still far from the average per capita consumption in the EU, which was 22.2 kg in 2019¹⁰.

Although the degree of self-sufficiency in poultry meat in Germany is still above 100% at 104.7%, it has decreased in recent years. The reasons for the lower degree of self-sufficiency are, on the one hand, difficulties in the approval of new fattening houses in Germany and, on the other hand, a voluntary reduction in stocking density by 10% due to the participation of fatteners in the "Initiative Tierwohl". The "Initiative Tierwohl" is a label of the food retail trade that distinguishes meat and milk products poultry, cattle and pork that come from a farm that participates in the initiative and implements the specified animal welfare criteria.

Despite the self-sufficiency level of over 100 %, cuts are imported, because breast meat in particular is in high demand. Wings and thighs, on the other hand, are partly exported, as sales in Germany are insufficient. In general, it can be said that chicken meat is mainly marketed as fresh meat from domestic slaughterhouses⁷.

The conventional production of broilers in Germany is characterised by a strong vertical integration in which parent flocks, hatcheries, contract farmers, own slaughterhouses as well as processing plants and also feed mills are in the hands of so-called integrations. The proportion of organically produced broilers is very small and only accounts for about 1.5% of the animals available on the market. Organic farms predominantly market their products through direct marketing or other channels.

Finally, it remains to be mentioned that the importance of quality seals and proofs of origin is clearly increasing¹¹.

⁷ DLG, 2022

⁸ Statistisches Bundesamt, 2020

⁹ Marktinfo Eier und Geflügel, 2017

¹⁰ BMEL-Statistik, 2020

¹¹ BMEL-Statistik, 2020

Overview and analysis of the German BroKIS

In the centre of the German BroKIS network map (Figure 7) there are the farmers. As mentioned at the beginning of this section, they are usually contractually bound to one of the integrations (top left in the picture). There are four active parties of this kind in the German market for conventional chicken. These integrations unite under their roof everything from the parent flock to the hatchery to slaughtering and marketing, and in addition, as already mentioned, the contractual commitment of the farmers. This results in a two-way flow of products between the integrations and the farmers, as chicks are delivered to the farmers and ready-to-slaughter animals go back to the integration. Regular knowledge transfers through seminars as well as veterinary support are guaranteed. The animals are slaughtered in the integration's own slaughterhouses and sold via the integrations to the food retailers (approx. 50 %) or to gastronomy and other bulk buyers.

Furthermore, there are farmers who fatten their animals for direct marketing and are thus not contractually bound. In the organic sector, farmers mostly participate in label programmes such as Bioland or Demeter. In addition to belonging to an integration, many farmers (approx. 95%) are also organised in producer organisations at state or national level. In these communities, for example, prices are negotiated with slaughterhouses for their members, the joint purchase of electricity and / or gas is agreed upon, or catching processes are jointly coordinated.

If you continue clockwise on the map, you will find the group of barn builder, who offer farmers their products and services for the construction and furnishing of the barns. There is also an exchange between this group and the scientific actors, as, for example, expert opinions on new products are prepared.

The group of the "Organisations, associations and NGOs" and media follows in the clockwise direction. The associations are German central Poultry association ("ZDG", in German: Zentralverband der Deutschen Geflügelwirtschaft e.V.) and the German Broiler association ("BVH", in German: Bundesverband bäuerlicher Hähnchenerzeuger e.V.). The associations are strongly connected, the „ZDG“ is the umbrella organization of the German poultry associations. The "BVH" is subordinate to the "ZDG" and is the German Industry partner from the BroilerNet and Co-leader of WP3 "Animal Welfare". The "BVH" is the representative in political matters and also provide input and knowledge to producer organisations, farmers, research institutes and media sources. The magazine "DGS – Magazin für die Geflügelwirtschaft" is the official organ of the „ZDG“, through which a great transfer of knowledge between practice and science is carried out.

the associated certification do not only include broiler farming per se. They often include the entire supply chain, from hatchery and feed production to slaughter and marketing. This report does not include “food service” because most operate internationally and are too broadly positioned for BINs. Smaller operations are covered with the integrations and producer organisations. Retailers have strong links with label programs, integrations and farmers. It is important to note that almost every retailer also own and sells its own brand und additionally other label products.

In the lower left area, the group “Academic, research and Governmental organisations” is located. Here, for example, are the universities, each of them as a more or less extensive research area on poultry and also cooperates with each other to varying degrees. However, there are relationships with other research institutions, Chamber of Agricultural, farmers and also network projects “Netzwerk Fokus Tierwohl”, which promotes the transfer of knowledge between science and practice. This project connected all Chamber of Agricultural and included all topics around farm animal welfare. Furthermore, there are Federal research institutions that are subordinate to the Federal ministry of Food and Agricultural. A great deal of knowledge is generated in this area, which is made available to other actors in the industry via media and direct interactions. There is also active cooperation with the legislator and, for example, an exchange of input through the processing of scientific reports. The legislator and its various implementing bodies (e.g., veterinary authorities) are in direct contact with the farmers and the integrations. Actors such as research societies “FFG – Frankenförder Forschungsgesellschaft mbH” deals with practical research and are in close contact with farmers and industry.

The last group presented in this circle is the veterinary and pharmaceutical sector. Although most farms are looked after by veterinarians of their integration, there are also independent poultry veterinarians on the market and of course companies that develop and offer various products for this area. So, there is knowledge and service from the Vets to the farmers. Pharma companies supply the vets and the farmers with their products and specific knowledge. They get input for this from the research area of the map. A good example here is Corbiota, a company that uses worms and worming products to strengthen the eubiosis of young animals such as chicks or piglets. They work together with academic partners for research in this field and have contact to farmers, who they do supply with their products.

We invited 5 key actors for validation and revise our actor map. The actors are listed below:

- BVH
- Lower Saxony Chamber of Agricultural
- FLI

- Farmer
- Project member of Netzwerk Fokus Tierwohl

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Germany

The German network shows complex structures and many different actors with different orientations and influences. In order to carry out the formation of the BINs, the actors should be chosen regardless of their influence. There are already stakeholders who has been asked to collaborate with the BroilerNet project and share their input or knowledge. For example, in Germany we will cooperate with the "Netzwerk Fokus Tierwohl", integrator "Sprehe", Crobiota and the "BVH" as well as the "FFG". This already covers four groups from our map. Additionally, there are interactions between FLI and the ITW (e.g. membering advisory board) and DTB ("Deutscher Tierschutzbund"). In this context, the stars as well as the number of stars on the actor map show the capacity of the individual actors that have been named here.

"Netzwerk Fokus Tierwohl" and "FFG" offer the use of existing structures to inform about the existence of *BroilerNet* but also to pass on specific questions or results to the practice. Furthermore, surveys and workshops can be planned together.

The FLI had the opportunity to present the *BroilerNet* project on several occasions, e.g., at the EuroTier in Hannover or exchange of experiences with project applications. These presentations have attracted attention to the project and have led to both old and new actors coming forward who would like to participate in the network.

Furthermore, there is a good cooperation with the producer associations, which will also be used to further develop the network. A workshop at the "BVH" is planned for January 25 in 2023. This workshop will take place after a meeting of the board of directors and will on the one hand present the project, but on the other hand it will also be about the exploration of challenges regarding the three main topics of the project (Environmental Sustainability, Animal Welfare, and Animal Health) and to arouse interest in active cooperation. From this meeting, which will be attended by representatives from the poultry industry from all over Germany, we hope for a wealth of direct contacts. Particularly in a large country like Germany, which functions completely differently from region to region due to its structuring into 16 federal states, it is important to be able to include representatives from all regions.

However, both the FLI and the BVH are in the north of the country, so by canvassing and recruiting contacts at a nationwide meeting, we hope to

have good coverage of all parts of the country without favouring our own catchment area.

For the topics "Environmental Sustainability" (WP2) and "Animal Welfare" (WP3) actors from all groups can be invited, as these topics are in the focus of society as well as in the economy. The broadness of the areas does not make the choice easy, but accordingly more diverse.

The situation is somewhat different for work package 4 on "Animal Health": Here, the stakeholders are available to a limited extent. However, here we have excellent contacts to the other institutes of the FLI as well as to the veterinary universities.

In addition to these contacts, which result from existing cooperation's of the FLI, we expect, as already mentioned, to be able to establish new contacts with producer groups and associations at the planned workshop and to be able to win experts from practice for each topic.

Some contacts still need to be made in specific groups to fully exploit the knowledge of the various stakeholders. Furthermore, it is more difficult to interact with some groups because some of them (e.g., integrations) are less eager to directly cooperate, e.g., due to the economic competition within the groups.

In some groups, there are still classic role distributions, with leadership positions mostly held by men and executive positions more likely to be held by women. For example, there are many women in livestock science and more men in integration companies. Through the interdisciplinary cooperation of different groups and actors, we can achieve a heterogeneous mixture, whereby the gender balance can be achieved.

3.4 Greece BroKIS

Introduction and country context

Over the past decades, the broiler industry in Greece has made tremendous progress to meet the growing demand for inexpensive and safe supply of high-quality meat in compliance with the EU and National Legislation on broiler welfare¹². This development was combined with structural changes in the sector, characterized by the modernization of farming facilities, the intensification of the farming system and the concentration of poultry farms¹³. The poultry industry is located mainly in the regions of Epirus

¹² Council Directive 2007/43/EC of 28 June 2007 laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production.

¹³ Dotas, Vassilios, et al. "Typology, Structural Characterization and Sustainability of Integrated Broiler Farming System in Epirus, Greece." *Sustainability* 13.23 (2021): 13084.

(Ioannina and Arta), Evia - Viotia - Attica and Macedonia. According to statistics (MRDF) recorded by the end of 2009, 66,2% of total broiler breeder farms and 45% of broiler farms have been located in Ioannina County¹⁴.

Main production system is conventional broiler farming. There is a small and decreasing part of organic chicken meat production. Free range broiler system is becoming popular especially in rural, mountainous areas of Greece. Recent studies reveal feeding cost and feed conversion ratio as strongly related variables with the technical and scale efficiency of farms in Epirus¹⁵.

Total number of broiler farms in Greece are 1042. The 89 breeder farms had, until the end of 2009, 358 flocks of hens, of which 303/358 (84.6%) consisted of broiler breeders, the 38/358 (10.6%) were mixed production flocks and 17/358 (4.7%) were layer breeders flocks.

The poultry industry is the most organized and fully integrated part of the animal sector in Greece with good prospects for growth and further development. Investments by the industry at all stages of production (feed mills, poultry farms, hatcheries, slaughterhouses) are continuous¹⁶¹⁷. There is a rough estimate of more than 100 million euros investments for 2021 – 2024.

Poultry meat consumption per capita reached 25.6 kg in 2019 in Greece, according to Faostat. This is 8.24% less than in the previous year. Historically, poultry meat consumption per capita in Greece reached an all-time high of 27.9 kg in 2018 and an all-time low of 1.47 kg in 1961.

According to AVEC¹⁴ domestic production of poultry meat in Greece for 2020 was 235.000 tons carcass weight. Self-sufficiency of the country is about 82%.

Overview and analysis of the Greek BroKIS

The Greek Ministry of Rural Development and Food is providing legal infrastructure for Greek broiler industry and verifies law implementation. The General Secretariat R&D provides funding for research cooperation between academia, research institutes, broiler industry and broiler farmers.

¹⁴ AVEC Annual Report 2021

¹⁵ Hatzizisis, L., et al. "Technical efficiency measurement in broiler chicken production system: a case study in Epirus, Greece." *Agricultural Economics Review* 20.1 (2019): 63-79.

¹⁶ Koutoulis, Konstantinos. "Present and future of poultry industry in Greece." *Proceedings of the 12th Pan-Hellenic Veterinary Congress, Athens, Greece*. 2012.

¹⁷ Xexaki, E.N.Sossidou, G.Filiouis and E.Petridou (2019). Current practices in Greek broiler farms as related to the technical status of the establishments and equipment

National Poultry Association is representing farmers and integrators and supports Government Institutions on decision making on broiler production.

There are 6 main broiler integrators, most of them provide their farmers with all required inputs (day old chicks, feed, veterinary service, etc). One of them has a very sophisticated circular economy structure and facilities and formidable research cooperation network. It also operates innovative broiler health monitoring systems with predictive capabilities. Some smaller companies lack strong Innovation orientation but still benefit from cooperation with bigger volume integrators. There is a major player on a turnover basis but with very low, if any, interaction with academia and research institutes. Main innovations of that integrator are being developed mainly through Input from suppliers cooperations. Another company used to be a big innovator some decades ago but recently decreased both volume of production and innovation effort. There is a company that stands for relatively small percentage of broiler production but has some successful innovative products mainly feed based. A key broiler integrator invests very small amount of effort and staff on knowledge and new practises.

Almost 12% of total broiler farms are free range, certified by AGROCERT, a certification authority under the umbrella of ELLINIKOS GEORGIKOS ORGANISMOS-DIMITRA (ELGO-DIMITRA). Agrocert is also involved in developing standards and schemes on broiler sector. It also disseminates relative information and trains farmers and integrators.

Broiler farmers range from small 5.000-15.000 birds with limited knowledge transfer, to bigger farms that are more willing to Innovate and adopt new technologies.

There is a strong interaction between various companies that provide supplies, infrastructure and innovative technological development to both farmers and integrators.

The Veterinary Research Institute of the ELLINIKOS GEORGIKOS ORGANISMOS-DIMITRA (VRI, ELGO-DIMITRA) is a key research player both for the broiler production and agricultural development in Greece. For over two decades, issues of high importance for the agricultural sector, such as integrated livestock management and development, environment and ecosystems protection, sustainable livestock production and breeding, organic agriculture, fisheries, forestry and public health protection etc. are approached in the spirit of agricultural research in the service of society and implemented with the application of new technologies. The target groups affected by the activity of the organization are farmers, consumers, educational organizations, local authorities, non-governmental organizations, research organizations / researchers, SMEs and students. More specifically, researchers of the Laboratory of Animal Health and Welfare of the Veterinary Research Institute, Main Actors/Partners in

BroilerNet, are expected to provide new knowledge and innovative solutions on all topics examined in the framework of the project such as broiler health and welfare, sustainable production systems, use of industrial by-products in broiler industry to reduce feed cost, etc¹⁸¹⁹²⁰²¹²²²³²⁴²⁵²⁶.

There are several companies that provide support and supplies for broiler health. They mainly interact with integrators and on very rare occasions directly to the farmers.

AB Vassilopoulos is a very dynamic major retailer of Greek market. The company has introduced broiler welfare requirements and is making a constant effort to estimating and reducing carbon footprint on broiler farm level. AB Vassilopoulos has a good research network with universities and mainly AFS.

¹⁸ Relić, R., Sossidou, E., Dedousi, A., Perić, L., Božičković, I., Đukić-Stojčić, M. (2019). Behavioral and health problems of poultry related to rearing systems, Ankara Universitesi Veteriner Fakultesi Dergisi, 66 (4), pp. 423-428, DOI: 10.33988/auvfd.597496

¹⁹ Tsiouris, V., Economou, E., Lazou, T., Georgopoulou, I., Sossidou, E. (2019). The role of whey on the performance and campylobacteriosis in broiler chicks, Poultry Science, 98 (1), pp. 236-243, DOI: 10.3382/ps/pey388

²⁰ Kasapidou, E., Sossidou, E.N., Zdragas, A., Papadaki, C., Vafeas, G., Mitlianga, P. (2016). Effect of grape pomace supplementation on broiler meat quality characteristics [Einfluss des Einsatzes von Weintraubentrestern auf die Qualität von Broilerfleisch], European Poultry Science, 80, DOI: 10.1399/Eps.2016.135

²¹ Evangelia Sossidou, Ludovic Toma Czijszter, Endre Szucs, Dinu Gavojdian (2015). Socio-Economic Framework of Farm Animal Welfare. ÁLLATTENYÉSZTÉS TAKARMÁNYOZÁS Hungarian Journal of Animal Production 2015, 64.2.: 81-93

²² Sossidou, E.N., Dal Bosco, A., Castellini, C., Grashorn, M.A. (2015). Effects of pasture management on poultry welfare and meat quality in organic poultry production systems, World's Poultry Science Journal, 71 (2), pp. 375-384, DOI: 10.1017/S0043933915000379.

²³ V. Dotas, D. Gourdouvelis, E.N. Sossidou, S. Kianas, L. Hatzizisis, D. Dotas (2014). Faba bean seeds ileal digestibility of energy, crude protein and aminoacids in broiler chickens, World's Poultry Science Journal, Volume 70, Supplement 1:49

²⁴ E.N. Sossidou (2013). Effects of pasture management on poultry welfare and meat quality in organic poultry production systems, Invited paper, World's Poultry Science Journal, Volume 69, supplement, ISSN 0043-9339: 11

²⁵ N. Sossidou, A. dal Bosco, H. A. Elson and C.M.G.A. Fontes (2011). Pasture based systems for poultry production: implications and perspectives, World's Poultry Science Journal, March 2011, Volume 67: 47-58

²⁶ E. N. Sossidou, P. Fortomaris, D. Kipourou, H. A. Elson and A. Tserveni-Goussi (2010). Organic broilers' preferences for different features of habitat in the outdoor areas, World's Poultry Science Journal, Volume 66, Supplement, ISSN 0043-9339: 313

Figure 8 Actors in the broiler sector in Greece and their relationships

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Greece

Researchers of the Veterinary Research Institute of ELGO-DIMITRA will be a vital part of the network as they bring expertise from previous research-networking projects. They will be contacted to provide participant (s). 20 broiler farmers will be selected upon willingness to cooperate and innovation application at their farms.

Retailers' experts (AB Vassilopoulos) will also bring an important contribution as they are leaders at welfare and environmental requirements. One or two AB Vassilopoulos experts will be invited.

Any input from companies that support broiler production will be of great value. Any Government and National Association participation will be welcomed.

Contacts with executives working for integrators will be very important for developing the network. So far, we see no conflict of interest.

Executives and scientists from companies that support broiler production will be invited as well.

3.5 Ireland BroKIS

Introduction and country context

The Irish poultry industry is comprised of the rearing of birds for meat and the keeping of table-egg laying flocks to produce eggs for human consumption, a network of breeding flocks and hatcheries to support these activities, egg packing centres and poultry processing plants²⁷. The poultry sector in its totality accounts for 2% of agricultural output. There are approximately 800 farms involved in commercial poultry production in Ireland. This is broken down into the following²⁷:

- 418 rearing poultry for meat
- 186 involved in table-egg production
- 170 breeding farms and hatcheries

Like many countries across the EU, the Irish poultry meat sector is highly integrated. There is seven export-approved slaughter plants, with a number of Local Authority approved plants also. However, there is three main integrators; Manor Farm, Western Brand and Shannon Vale Foods.

Total meat consumption per capita had been declining in Ireland in the earl 2000s and this was worsened by the recession. However, a recovery has been seen since 2012. According to Central Statistic Office (CSO) data, 42.3% of the meat consumed in Ireland is poultry meat (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Meat consumption in Ireland per species.

Source: CSO Ireland
Highcharts.com

In terms of support, there is government support to producers. The Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) offer an investment scheme (Pig & Poultry Investment Scheme) for renovations to older houses

²⁷ DAFM 2019

to improve efficiency and animal welfare. There is also a tariff scheme to promote the change from fossil fuels to renewable fuels for non-domestic businesses, this includes poultry farms. This is offered by the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI). This tariff is paid based on the heat produced using renewable fuels for a period of 15 years.

Overview and analysis of the Irish BroKIS

The map above shows the companies, organisations, stakeholders and integrators involved in the Irish broiler sector. AS outlined previously, there are three main integrators – Manor Farm, Western Brand and Shannon Vale Foods.

Figure 10. Actors in the broiler sector in Ireland and their relationships

Manor Farm is the largest of these integrators. They own and run Kolbe Feeds, a feed mill dedicated to the production of broiler feed solely for Manor Farm. Their breeder units are supplied with feed from A.W. Ennis. Annyalla Chicks Ltd is the hatchery for Manor Farm, hatching all of their broilers. In terms of veterinary services, Agrihealth work closely with Manor Farm to manage their farms. Sicin Co-op is a co-operative group established by the growers of Manor Farm. These growers work together to achieve competitive prices for inputs such as gas, litter, etc.

Western Brand is the next largest integrator. Western Brand own and manage their hatchery, supplied with hatching eggs from their breeder farms. Western Brand purchases feed from four feed mills across Ireland; Paul & Vincent’s, Corby Rock Milling, Kiernan Milling, and Bandon Feed Mill.

St David's Poultry Team works with Western Brand growers and breeders on their animal health, vaccinations and all other welfare areas.

Shannon Vale Foods is the third and final integrator. Shannon Vale, similar to Western Brand, have their own hatchery. Feed is purchased from Kiernan Milling and Corby Rock Milling. St David's Poultry Team again provide veterinary services to Shannon Vale Foods.

In terms of regulation, the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM) is responsible for implementing the legislation and regulations. DAFM also has a regulator role over the feed mills, ensuring all legislations are abided by.

For planning regulations, each county has a local County Council who oversees all planning applications ensuring all standards are adhered to. The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) becomes involved when a site has greater than 40,000 birds on site. Should this situation arise, the producer must apply for Integrated Pollution Control (IPC) license.

Bord Bia is the Irish Quality Assurance board. Each farm, grower or breeder, supplying to the three afore mentioned integrators, must be Bord Bia Quality Assured. This involved animal welfare, animal health and sustainability. This quality assurance allows a premium price for Irish products, it is also a great USP when exporting.

In terms of the sale and distribution of our Irish produce, there is a number of supermarket chains, wholesalers (Musgraves) who supply to more supermarkets, fast-food restaurants and also some small local restaurants.

The Irish Farmers' Association (IFA) is a farmer organisation who lobby on multiple issues on behalf of their members. This groups often lobbies in relation to a fair price for produce.

Poultry Ireland is a stakeholder group. This group has many representatives from all of the poultry sectors. This group was established during a high risk period of disease. The aim of the group is to be 'One Voice' for the poultry sector on many issues when communicating with DAFM, local county councils, EPA and other relevant bodies.

Teagasc is an advisory, education and research body representing all areas of agriculture. Teagasc communicates with the integrators directly, producers, producer groups, IFA, DAFM, Bord Bia, EPA, veterinary companies and the stakeholder group. Teagasc offers educational courses to producers on poultry management. They also offer advice on planning permission issues, environmental issues, DAFM and SEAI funding, among other topics.

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Ireland

Innovation Networks, or discussion groups as they are commonly known, are quite popular in Ireland through Teagasc. DAFM also incentivised farmers' involvement in Knowledge Transfer (KT) Programmes. These KT programmes ran for 3 years, where farmers were expected to attend a minimum of six meetings and a national event on there are of agriculture. Unfortunately, once the incentive was removed some of these groups dissipated. However, some producers would like these discussion groups to return.

One area which would be of concern for the creation of a BIN in Ireland, is the combining of producers from the different integrators and the sharing of information, particularly financial information. However, the Themes of this project should remove this concern, as financial information can be shared confidentially with the facilitator.

Overall, the industry are interested in this project, as it is an excellent opportunity to learn from our colleagues in Europe.

The integrators have been communicated with on their producers involvement in this project and are happy for their participation. The establishment of this BIN will not be a first for Ireland, however, the sharing of information with our European counterparts will be through this type of network.

Teagasc is the academic partner for Ireland, however, they will also be the facilitator for the BIN. There is great experience within Teagasc on KT groups, innovation networks and discussion groups.

Due to Teagasc's close communication with many of the actors in the broiler sector, involving these organisations in the project should not prove too difficult. The IFA have committees in each area of the poultry sector, as a result we can link with these groups to establish the BIN.

The EPA have introduced new regulations surrounding planning applications with 10km of Natura 2000 sites. These are Special Areas of Constraint (SAC's) and Special Protected Area's (SPA's). Due to the distribution of the poultry sector in Ireland, this change in regulation is having a major impact to existing and potentially new growers. The reason for this new regulation is as a result of ammonia emissions. This is a key area of concern for growers and EPA alike, therefore, the theme of sustainability will be of interest to the industry.

Bord Bia will be keen to see producers engaging on the topics of animal health and welfare, as this is part of the requirement to be quality assured. Bord Bia are focused on promoting a positive image for our sector, therefore, the involvement in this project will be of interest

Teagasc will engage with Western Brand and Manor Farm growers to begin with due to their location and proximity to the Teagasc facilitators' base. The standard model for Teagasc discussion groups is to have 12 – 15 members per group. This group will meet 8 – 10 times per annum and usually take an excursion together. This will be the model put into practice for the BIN. For the engagement with the wider industry, Teagasc has a good relationship with many stakeholders. This will allow interaction between the BIN and veterinary companies, feed mills, vaccine companies, energy companies, DAFM and other regulatory bodies.

3.6 Italy BroKIS

Introduction and country context

The Italian production of poultry meat accounted 1,374,100 tons in 2021, (+1.14% compared to 2020); per capita consumption stood at 21.43 kg. The Italian poultry sector confirmed excellent levels of self-sufficiency, resulting overall self-sufficient at 108.4%. Italy produces 105.6% of the chicken meat consumed in our Country and 120.8% of the turkey meat. Italy is confirmed as the fifth European producer of poultry meat after Poland, Germany, France, and Spain.

The overall turnover of the national poultry meat and egg sector in 2021 amounted to approximately 5,900 million euros (4,830 million for meat, 1,070 million for eggs), confirming the leading role played by the Italian poultry supply chain in the national agribusiness. There are approximately 64,000 people employed in the farming phase (38,500) and in the transformation of meat and eggs (25,500).

Consumption by product type stabilized in 2021, after the increase in products with high added value (raw and cooked and breaded and packaged preparations) recorded in 2020 and largely due to the particular situation created by the Covid-19 pandemic which led consumers to buy more easily storable products.

Poultry meat exports recorded a good recovery in 2021 (i.e., increased by +8.3%, while imports increased by +5.5%) after the generalized contraction of foreign trade occurred in 2020 due to the global pandemic situation.

Considering the balance between exports (198,793 tons) and imports (91,798), consumption stood at 1,267,100 tons (1,293,300 in 2020), equal to a per capita consumption of 21.43 kg, -0.5% compared to 21.55 kg in 2020 (year of the lockdown) and +1.3% compared to 2019.

With regard to consumption by type of poultry meat, the share of chicken meat in 2021 increased by 76.9% (against 74.2% in 2020), the one of

turkey meat fell (19.5% against the previous 22.5 %) whereas the one of other poultry meat increases slightly (from 3.3% to 3.6%). Poultry is the only one self-sufficient livestock sector in Italy.

However, the AI epidemic in 2022 has contracted the production of poultry, especially turkey, so that the self-supply rate is expected to decrease to 98%.

Overview and analysis of the Italian BroKIS

AIA, Amadori and Fileni are the 3 main Italian producers of poultry meat, accounting 85% of the national production and they produce over 90% of the turkey meat (there is only one other turkey producer in Italy). They are the most influential actors in driving the market, out of the 27 producers reported in the network map (Figure 11). Ten producers are fully integrated and therefore have complete control over the entire poultry meat supply chain, from breeders to processing plants; the others are classified as producers because missing the breeder/hatchery and/or the slaughterhouse and/or the feed mill. Four actors keep broiler breeders and are equipped with hatcheries to produce Day Old Chicks (DOCs), thus provide rural and industrial farmers. Main relationships are related to "input" (i.e., poultry feed) and "output" (i.e., DOCs) exchanges; biggest actors also share "services" intended as slaughter service.

Several producers are well motivated to take part actively to BroilerNet as they are considering this project as a great opportunity to discuss innovation needs for the broiler sector and to find and share the best available practices to meet those needs.

Knowledge and innovations in the field of poultry health are provided and disseminated in Italy by the academic and public health institutions (Faculties of Veterinary, Ministry of Health and its IZSs Zooprophyllactic Experimental Regional Institutes, Competent Authority for Animal Health). However, the main provider of animal health related knowledge in Italy is SIPA (Italian Society of Avian Pathology), which the vast majority of Italian practitioner vets involved in the poultry sector are associated to. An annual conference is organized every year by SIPA and relevant proceedings are published. Competent Authority for Animal Health can be represented in BroilerNet by dr. Galuppo Francesco, expert in poultry biosecurity measures.

Poultry welfare related knowledge is spread by academic and public health institutions (i.e., Faculties of Veterinary and Agriculture, Ministry of Health and its IZSs Zooprophyllactic Experimental Regional Institutes, Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forests and its Centre for agricultural research and analysis of agricultural economics).

Knowledge and innovation in the field of the environmental sustainability of poultry farming is spread by fewer actors, compared with animal health and welfare. Academic institutions such as the faculties of Agriculture and Veterinary are the main providers, together with the Center for agricultural research and analysis of agricultural economics, the University of Bologna and CRPA.

Figure 11 Actors in the broiler sector in Italy and their relationships

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Italy

The Italian key actors are likely to perceive the project as an opportunity to exchange views across EU about the challenges of the sector and how are addressed by each member EU Member State.

The three main actors of the Italian poultry meat supply chain do welcome BroilerNet, so they are supposed to be willing to take part actively to this project.

Main challenges to ensure active participation of Italian key actors can be related to their lack of time availability in joining the BIN's meetings. Thus, special attention should be paid to organize BIN's meetings, in-presence and online, sufficiently in advance to allow participants to organize themselves in time.

Lack of trust could be a challenge for farmers to spread their best practices. Special attention should be paid by the Italian BIN's facilitator to emphasize the value of the innovative knowledge that farmers can access in return for the provision by them of information and good practices.

Large retailers and animal protection NGOs could be successfully involved in the process of identifying innovation needs, although they will probably not be able to provide evidence of good practices to address the challenges of the broiler sector; breeders, veterinarians and technicians are the ones to be most involved. Coop Italia is one of the 3 largest retailers in Italy with high interest in complying with upgraded standards of environmental sustainability and animal welfare. Compassion in World Farming (CIWF) is one of the most active NGOs for animal protection in Italy and also the most “collaborative” one in working together with the livestock supply chain to improve animal welfare above the minimum requirements of the EU legislation.

The following actors are proposed to be invited to join the meetings of the Italian BIN because they are acknowledged as the main actors of the Italian poultry sector or providers of technical and scientific knowledge to run poultry farming innovatively.

- 24 Italian producers, mentioned in the map
- SIPA
- University of Milan
- University of Bologna
- CReNBA
- Centre for agricultural research and analysis of agricultural economics
- Istituto Zootecnico Sperimentale delle Venezie (IZSve)
- Coop Italia
- Compassion In World Farming (CIWF)
- Competent Authority for Animal Health

Integrators will be asked to participate and invite their advisors with skills in the 3 main innovation topics addressed by BroilerNet.

3.7 Netherlands BroKIS

Introduction and country context

The Netherlands is the 6th main poultry producer in the EU with a share of 7% of the total EU broiler meat production, equivalent to 869 tonnes per year in 2021²⁸. In the Netherlands, in June 2022, there were 70 broiler breeder rearing farms with 2.8 million birds, 190 production farms with 5 million birds, and 640 broiler farms with 49 million birds. Fourteen broiler hatcheries producing 13-14 million day-old chickens per week were present in the Netherlands and 14 slaughter plants with a production of 1.085.00 tons of meat, and 85 factories producing 3 million tons of poultry feed, of which about half of this amount is for broiler production.

²⁸ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-02/poultry-meat-dashboard_en_0.pdf

Yearly consumption in the Netherlands is 20.6 kg per person per year. Regarding the economic value of the broiler production chain, we refer to Van Horne and Benus, 2022²⁹. Export of poultry meat from The Netherlands is mainly to other EU countries, of which the majority is exported to Germany, UK, Belgium, France and Denmark (72% of total amount exported). Export to countries outside EU was 12% of total export volume in 2021³⁰.

The Dutch broiler sector has a diversity in production systems³⁰. More than 95% of the farms is a member of the 'IKB quality control program'. In addition to the conventional broiler production systems, where fast-growing breeds (mainly Ross 308) are housed fully indoors under relatively high stocking densities (39-42 kg/m²), there are other production systems present with higher welfare requirements. The most dominant alternative production systems is the 'Beter Leven one star' system which is a free range indoor system³¹) and for which the criteria are defined by the Dutch Society for Animal Protection. Most important characteristics of these farms are the use of a slower-growing breed which is slaughtered at a minimum age of 56 days. These birds are housed at a stocking density of 25 kg/m² maximum, are provided with bales and grains and a covered veranda (20% of floor area). All houses have daylight entrance of at least 3% of the floor area. This 'Beter Leven one star' production system will become the dominant production system for all fresh meat sold by Dutch retail by 2023, as from then onwards this will be the minimum standard in retail for fresh meat³². In addition to retail, a large part of food service companies will switch to this type of production. This means that the proportion of broilers (from the total number of broilers present in the Netherlands) housed according to this system will grow from 5-10% in 2020 until about 60-80% in 2025³³. Currently there is therefore a transition towards more farms producing according to this system. Already since several years broiler meat from the conventional system is not being sold any more by retail (fresh meat). Various production systems with slower-growing breeds were present in the Netherlands such as 'Kip van Morgen' and 'Nieuwe Standaard Kip' but these are thus gradually replaced by the 'Beter Leven one star' production system. Organic production has a relatively low market share in the Netherlands, only 0.5% in 2020³³.

²⁹ P.L.M. van Horne and A.M. Benus, 2022. Pluimveevleessector in Nederland: feiten en cijfers over pluimveevlees. <https://research.wur.nl/en/publications/pluimveevleessector-in-nederland-feiten-en-cijfers-over-pluimveev>

³⁰ Stadig, L. 2019. VLEESKUIKENCONCEPTEN IN NEDERLAND Een vergelijking op gebied van dierenwelzijn. Den Haag: Dierenbescherming

³¹ <https://beterleven.dierenbescherming.nl/over-de-dieren/alle-dieren/vleeskuikens/>

³² <https://www.nieuweoogst.nl/nieuws/2022/08/29/vleeskuikenhouderij-wacht-nog-flinke-inspanning-bij-overstap-beter-leven>

³³ Rapport-visie-op-pluimvee_tcm16-116992.pdf (abnamro.nl)

Antibiotics usage in the broiler sector in the Netherlands has largely decreased since 2009, as the sector is actively working towards reduction of usage³⁴ In general, systems with slower growing strains have a lower antibiotics usage as compared to systems with conventional strains³⁵ Therefore, the change towards Beter Leven one star being the dominant production system helps to further reduce antibiotics usage.

Current important issues in the broiler sector in the Netherlands are the continuing threat of Avian Influenza, which has become endemic, and the need to reduce the Nitrogen emissions for the whole agricultural sector. Poultry farms are an important source of fine dust and endotoxins, which is an important issue with respect to public health³.

Overview and analysis of the Dutch BroKIS

The actors in the Dutch broiler sector are shown in Figure 12, along with their relationships. (Note that specific companies are mentioned as examples, and that this overview is not complete.) An important characteristic of the Dutch broiler sector is that the broiler sector is not integrated and in this sense, it differs from the largely integrated broiler sectors in other countries. However, with the change towards the majority of broiler production from Beter Leven one star production systems, the level of integration increased. Apart from the Netherlands being a large broiler meat producer, there are many international companies related to poultry production in the Netherlands, such as companies developing and selling housing equipment, climate computers, feed, slaughtering machines, pharma, etc. Several slaughter plants are not only present in the Netherlands but also in surrounding countries, such as Plukon Food Group and 2 Sisters Storteboom.

34 van Horne, P. L. M., and A. M. Benus. Pluimveevleessector in Nederland: feiten en cijfers over pluimveevlees. Wageningen Economic Research, 2022.

³⁵ <https://www.avined.nl/nieuws/sectorrapportage-antibiotica-2021-gepubliceerd>

Advisors from equipment, climate, nutrition companies and veterinary practices have an important role in farm management. We will use a targeted approach to include representatives of these group in the BIN's. Upon advice of our industry partner in BroilerNet, Wageningen Research, and farmer members of the BIN's, we will recruit specific advisors that can contribute to the aims of the BroilerNet project.

3.8 Poland BroKIS

Introduction and country context

Poland, since 2012 has been the EU leader in poultry meat production, with a share of 20% of EU production in the years 2017-2022. Poland is the second largest exporter to the EU; the production is about 2 million tons of broiler meat per year. Moreover, domestic production and export have been growing for years due to the growing broiler population, reaching 1 778.8 million heads in 2020. However, from 2021 broiler population decreased by 23,9%. Nevertheless, broiler chicken remains the most popular type of poultry farming.

Figure 13 shows Poland's broiler population size from 2005-2022³⁶. The number of broiler chickens increased from 501.3 million in 2005 to 897.6 million in 2022 (79%). On average, in the analyzed period, the stock of broilers increased by almost 43.5 million birds. However, the more significant stock increase increased within seven years (2014-2020) by 47%.

³⁶ EU Statistics

Figure 13. Population of broilers in Poland in 2014-2021 in millions

In 2020, there were 70,105 broiler farms in Poland (compared to 91,100 broiler farms in 2010, i.e., 23% less)³⁷. Most (97.1%) keep at most 500 broilers (Table 3). Flocks of 500 to 4,999 birds account for 0.2% of farms, only 0.1% of farms keep between 5,000 and 9,999 broilers, and the biggest flocks (10,000 broilers and more) account for 2.6% of farms (Table 3). According to the agricultural census conducted in 2020, 98.1% of broilers were on large-scale production farms, i.e., 10,000 and more.

Table 3. Characteristics of the polish broiler farms in 2020

Size of the broiler flock (In numbers)	Number of farms	Share of farms (%)	Size of broiler population (No of birds)	Share of broiler population (%)
1 - 49	64 075	91,4	694 646	0,7
50 - 149	3 755	5,4	237 855	0,2
150 - 499	228	0,3	49 335	0,0
500 - 1999	52	0,1	49 360	0,0
2000 - 4999	72	0,1	224 383	0,2
5000 - 9999	87	0,1	658 633	0,7
10000 and more	1 836	2,6	98 511 778	98,1
Total	70 105	100,0	100 425 990	100,0

³⁷ Agricultural census 2020

In the Mazowieckie and Wielkopolskie voivodships (Figure 14), the most significant number of farms producing broilers and the largest population of birds are located, the total share of the broiler population in 2020 was 38.4% (in 2010, 29.6%).

The data of the agricultural census carried out in 2020 show that in 2020, 23.5% of the broiler population was kept on farms with an agricultural area of up to one ha (in 2010 - 19.6%). In addition, the share of the broiler population on farms in the area group of 100 ha and more increased from 13.7% in 2010 to 14.2% in 2020. Large-scale production is being concentrated. Broiler meat production in Poland is constantly growing (Figure 15).

Figure 14. Regional diversification of broiler production in Poland in 2020

Figure 15. Broiler meat production in Poland 2005-2022³⁶

Poultry meat production increased from 1.4 million tonnes in 2014 to 2.2 million tonnes in 2020, i.e. by 48.9%. The most significant increase in meat production was recorded in 2016 (13% compared to 2015). According to the data of the Central Statistical Office, in 2020 the consumption of poultry meat per capita amounted to 29.2 kg. This is almost 1 kg more than the year 2019³⁸ (Table 4).

Table 4. Poultry meat production in Poland

Specification	Volumes per year								
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Broiler meat production in tons	1477	1 635	1 850	1 937	2 080	2 111	2 200	2 097	1658
Change 2014 =100	100	110.7	125.3	131.1	140.8	142.9	149.0	142.0	112.3
Change Previous year =100	100	110.7	113.1	104.7	107.4	101.5	104.2	95.3	79.1

A constant threat is bird flu, which usually attacks during the migration of wild birds. In the spring of 2022, there was not such a violent attack as in the previous year (only 27 outbreaks of avian influenza). Still, the autumn of 2022 brought the first outbreak of HPAI in a flock of 1,677 birds (mainly geese) in the Łódź Voivodeship in September 2022. New factors that may influence production include rising production costs, inflation and difficulties in access to feed and electricity, gas and coal. The rising fuel and electricity prices may call into question the profitability of continuing poultry farming and subsequent placements of broilers. Inflation is also a concern, as it may lead to a reduction in demand for overpriced poultry meat and thus lead to the bankruptcy of many poultry farmers.

According to the Regulation (EC) 853/2004 in 2021 there were about 124 approved poultry slaughterhouses operating. 20% of them were large meat producers others were working only locally. In recent years the number of slaughterhouses had decreased significantly.

Overview and analysis of the Polish BroKIS

The map in figure 16 provides a good overview of the Broiler sector in Poland. There are several actors involved in the Broiler Meat Supply Chain. Categories of the main actors and approximate numbers are listed below:

- Feed Suppliers: 5 very large, 30-40 other
- Hutcheries: 5 large, about 55 other
- Producers (farmers), including:

³⁸ Statistics Poland.

- Marketing groups – 26,
- Ltd companies – 22,
- Cooperatives – 6
- Individual producers – about 70000
- Farmers Unions and Organizations: at least 8
 - ✓ Polski Związek Zrzeszeń Hodowców i Producentów Drobiu (PZZHiPD)
 - ✓ Poldrób Ogólnopolski Związek Producentów Drobiu (Poldrób OZPD)
 - ✓ Krajowa Federacja Hodowców Drobiu i Producentów Jaj (KFHDiPJ)
 - ✓ Krajowa Rada Drobiarstwa – Izba Gospodarcza (KID)
 - ✓ Polska Federacja Hodowców Drobiu (PFHD)
 - ✓ Krajowa Izba Producentów Drobiu i Pasz (KIPDiP)
 - ✓ Zrzeszenie Producentów i Hodowców Drobiu (ZPiHD)
 - ✓ Światowe Stowarzyszenie Wiedzy Drobiarskiej (with Polski Oddział Światowego Stowarzyszenia Wiedzy Drobiarskiej) – World Association of Poultry Science
- Slaughterhouses – 101;
- Processors – to be identified
- Wholesale (selling meat) to be identified
- Retailers:
 - ✓ Hypermarket chains – 7 (316 stores)
 - ✓ Supermarkets – 4544
 - ✓ Large food stores – 7 283
 - ✓ Medium size food stores – 26 703
 - ✓ Farmers markets, Sunday markets, ... - approximately 500-600
- Gastronomy:
 - ✓ Main Fast Food Chains – 5
 - ✓ Numerous restaurants, catering
- Consumer Federation
- Research (Universities, Research Institutes): – 8 (large)
 - ✓ SGGW w Warszawie
 - ✓ Uniwersytet Przyrodniczy w Poznaniu
 - ✓ Uniwersytet Warmińsko-Mazurski w Olsztynie
 - ✓ Uniwersytet Rolniczy w Krakowie
 - ✓ Uniwersytet Przyrodniczy w Lublinie
 - ✓ Politechnika Bydgoska (Faculty of Animal Sciences)
 - ✓ Zachodniopomorski Uniwersytet Technologiczny w Szczecinie (Faculty of Biotechnology and Animal Sciences)
 - ✓ Instytut Zootechniki PIB in Balice
- Public Extension Service: 16 centres, one in each province
- Public Administration:
 - ✓ General Veterinary Inspectorate (GIW)

- ✓ Provincial veterinary inspectorate (16)
- ✓ District veterinary inspectorate (306)
- ✓ Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
- NGOs: 5

Some actors are generally presented to keep this map clear. Specifying all links (relationships) between so many actors is hard. We agree with the strength of connections between actors. The potential motivation and capacity of actors are still to check. Representatives of the PZZHiPD, SGGW (Animal Sciences Faculty), and GIW were engaged to validate and revise the map.

Figure 16. Actors in the broiler sector in Poland and their relationships.

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Poland

Key actors who should be involved in relevance to the project are identified, and some agreed already (50%) to participate in BIN. They have capacity and motivation because they are professionally involved in broiler production or its control.

There is only an informal network among members of poultry farmers' organisations. Organisations are not cooperative; they are strongly independent.

Some actors are very busy, and it would be a challenge (in GIW) to engage them. Moreover, some actors expect financial support for broiler production

in implementing innovations due to the project; they lose interest when they discover that it is only knowledge development and sharing.

3.9 Portugal BroKIS

Introduction and country context

Poultry meat is the main meat consumed in Portugal since 2020, the year in which it surpassed pork meat, which has always been the leader in consumption. The per capita consumption of chicken meat in Portugal is the highest in Europe. Production is very concentrated (more than 80% of production is produced by 1.5% of farms), based on the vertical integration system, with the 2 largest groups - Lusiaves and Valouro - representing around 60% of national production. Only 1% of production is made in organic production, but extensive systems, associated with voluntary quality certification systems, have progressively gained weight in the market, representing around 10% of consumption. Exports have also been growing significantly (more than 30% per year in the last 3 years) but the sector is in deficit, due to the import of "pieces" (mainly breast) since in terms of whole carcasses it has a surplus.

HIGHLIGHTS OF THE PORTUGUESE BROILER SECTOR 2021

NUMBER OF SPECIALIZED EXPLOITATIONS: +/- 860

AVERAGE ECONOMIC SIZE PER HOLDING: +/- 355 000 €

PRODUCTION (number): 212 095 000; (tons): 302 794 000

SLAUGHTER: (number): 199 593 000 ; (tons): 284 797

CONSUMPTION: 34.5 Kg/inhabitant . year

SELF-PROVISION RATE: 90%

EXTERNAL TRADE (MEAT AND CHICKEN OFFALS)

IMPORTS: 41 620 429 Ton / 79 147 375 €

EXPORTS: 26 299 723 Ton / 36 398 700 €

BALANCE: - 15 320 706 Ton / - 42 748 675 €

INTEGRATION SYSTEM IN THE POULTRY SECTOR IN PORTUGAL

Overview and analysis of the Portuguese BroKIS

On this map are all the main public, private and associative organizations that move and influence the poultry meat sector in Portugal. At the corporate level, they represent, together, more than 85% of the total production of chicken meat and about 75% of food distribution in Portugal. At the associative level, all the main national organizations that represent the production, processing and consumption of meat are integrated, including the main organic farming organization in the country (AGROBIO) and the main farmers' confederation (CAP) and the national consumer's association (DECO).

Figure 17. Actors in the broiler sector in Portugal and their relationships

In terms of food distribution and trade, in addition to the SONAE and Jerónimo Martins groups, responsible for around 60% of food distribution in Portugal, there are other operators that have been emerging as alternatives with growing expression and with specific characteristics that have qualitatively influenced the sector.

The national authorities included in the map include the GPP - national body responsible for defining policies and relations with the EU, the DGAV - national veterinary authority, the DGADR - responsible for quality and certification policies and the APA - environmental authority for licensing and environmental and waste control.

In terms of research and training, the main universities that have worked most directly with the sector are identified, as well as the INIAV - National Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Research.

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Portugal

The structure of the Portuguese BroKIS is rather complex and the number of actors is large. Furthermore, the organisation ANCAVE (Poultry Meat National representative) is fairly small. Therefore, it can be difficult to find a BNF that can dedicate enough time for BroilerNet work. The larger number of rather small actor can also pose a challenge when to interconnecting the different actors in order to form the Portuguese BIN.

Nevertheless, ANCAVE has a good overview and strong network for establishing a fully functional BIN with diverse expertise and dedicated actors. ANCAVE will collaborate with the FMV at Lisbon University, and this will facilitate the performance of BroilerNet, as FMV have previous experience of working in European projects.

3.10 Slovenia BroKIS

Introduction and country context

According to the Slovenian government data, poultry meat production has reached around 8% of the total value of agriculture and around 18 % within livestock production in the last decade.

In 2021, the production of Slovenian poultry meat amounted to over 72.200 tons of carcass weight (Figure 18).

Figure 18 The production of Slovenian poultry meat over the years³⁹ ()

Vir: Statistični urad Republike Slovenije

Despite periodic fluctuations the domestic consumption of poultry meat has been steadily increasing in the last decade and reached a record 66.200 tons in 2020. In 2021 decreased to 65.200 tons. The consumption of poultry meat per inhabitant amounted to 31 kg in 2021. Poultry meat represents the largest share of meat production in Slovenia (Figure 19 *poultry meat*, - *beef meat*, - *pig meat*)

Figure 19 Slovenian meat production³⁹

REPUBLIKA SLOVENIJA
STATISTIČNI URAD

Poultry meat production is the most export-oriented of all types of meat in Slovenia. In 2021, the export of poultry meat amounted to 34.830 tons.

³⁹ SURS, 2023

Poultry meat is the main export good, but since 2015, the export of poultry products (II stage of processing) has also increased significantly.

Slovenia has constant surpluses in poultry meat. The level of self-sufficiency in poultry meat has been growing since 2015. In 2021, it amounted to 112% (in 2020: 111%).

Commercial production of broiler meat in Slovenia is organized in three companies:

- Perutnina Ptuj,
- Pivka Perutninarstvo and
- Panvita Agromerkur.

The largest share is held by Perutnina Ptuj with 60 %, Pivka Perutninarstvo with 20 % and Panvita Agromerkur with 15 %. These three companies account for more than 95% of total broiler production in Slovenia. The rest is local, small backyard production.

All three companies are vertically organized. Each company covers a different part of the country, so there is not much geographical overlap.

The integrators have their own production of feed, parent stock, hatcheries, and slaughterhouses. Integrators provide feed, DOC, veterinary and technical support to farmers. Broilers are raised by farmers who are part of the respective vertically integrated chain. The majority of farmers are members of cooperatives, but there are also farmers who have a direct contract with integrators.

It is *estimated* that there are about 400 farmers in Slovenia for commercial production of broilers. The average size of the farms is 1,000 m². The majority of farmers own only one barn. Chicken farming is in many cases not the main occupation of farmers, as they also have other agricultures or animals. Recently, some larger farms with several houses are also built.

Overview and analysis of the Slovenian BroKIS

There are several actors involved in the Broiler Meat Supply Chain:

- Perutnina Ptuj Group (PP)
- Biotechnical Faculty (BF)
- Poultry cooperative Ptuj
- Association of Poultry Breeders
- Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia (CAFS)
- Veterinary clinic of Perutnina Ptuj Group (VCP)
- GIZ Meat industry of Slovenia
- Pivka
- Panvita

- Veterinary Faculty (VF)
- Faculty of Agriculture and Life Sciences (FKBV)
- Mercator
- Spar
- Hofer
- Lidl
- McDonald's (McD)
- Perutnina Ptuj feed mill
- Perutnina Ptuj Group hatchery
- Pivka hatchery
- Pivka feed mill
- Jata Emona feed mill
- Panvita feed mill
- Panvita hatchery
- Agricultural cooperative of poultry farmers Pivka (AC Pivka)
- Agricultural cooperative Agrosad (AC Agrosad)
- Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia (CCIS)

In most cases, members are part of one out of three integration chains. There are strong networks within each chain/integrator, but collaboration between integrations is occasional and opportunistic as there are competitors in the market. They are all part of the GIZ Meat Industry (GIZ MI), but this association also includes other meat producers in Slovenia (pork and beef). GIZ MI is a member of the AVEC association and a member of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia, CCIS.

On the side of farmers, there is a stronger network, especially between farmers who are united in cooperatives.

The Poultry Cooperative Ptuj is closely connected with the Veterinary Clinic PP, which is under the auspices of the Perutnina Ptuj Group. In the Poultry Cooperative Ptuj unites 149 breeders who deliver their bred broilers to Perutnina Ptuj. The same applies to the Agricultural Cooperative Agrosad, which has only 13 breeders as members, making it the smallest cooperative in Slovenia. The Perutnina Ptuj Group, together with all the breeders, raises 30 million chickens annually, which corresponds to about 50 thousand tons of meat. Statistics show that the company is growing over the years and the number of broilers bred is increasing. Geographically, the Perutnina Ptuj company covers the largest part of Slovenia (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Area demonstration of broiler breeders of Perutnina Ptuj (in Slovenia).

The Pivka company maintains a close relationship with the Agricultural cooperative of poultry farmers Pivka, an association of 52 breeders (Figure 21). Annually they breed a little more than 8 million chickens, which results in more than 12 thousand tons of meat.

Figure 21. Area demonstration of broiler breeders of Pivka company (in Slovenia).

Panvita Agromerkur is the smallest company in Slovenia engaged in poultry breeding. They breed about 5 million animals per year, which corresponds to 7 thousand tons of meat. The company has signed contracts with 30 breeders from whom it buys bred animals (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Area demonstration of broiler breeders of Panvita (in Slovenia).

At the national level, the Association of Poultry Breeders was established in 2021 as part of Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia (CAFS). So far, not much has been seen of this new association. The main goal was to balance the power of integrators.

All integrators work with retail chains. Lidl, Hofer, Spar, Mercator and McDonald's represent the majority of poultry meat sales in Slovenia. The producers require the integrators to meet certain standards, which are strictly controlled and to which the companies must adhere.

The Veterinary Clinic of the Perutnina Ptuj Group is under the auspices of the Perutnina Ptuj Group and occasionally cooperates with the Veterinary Faculty of the University of Ljubljana.

At the national level, there are three research and educational institutions that are directly linked to companies. These are the Biotechnical Faculty and the Veterinary Faculty of the University of Ljubljana and the Faculty of Agriculture and Life Sciences of the University of Maribor. All research and educational institutions are connected with the Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia (CAFS). They exchange knowledge and services among themselves.

CAFS is the umbrella interest organization of natural and legal persons in Slovenia engaged in agriculture, forestry and fishery. Its central task is to protect and represent their interests, to consult them and accelerate economical and environment friendly activities. CAFS is also actively involved in international activities. It is a member of Copa Cogeca and it participates on international conferences, congresses, fairs and preserves and strengthens good interaction with the agricultural organizations within and outside EU.

Figure 23. Actors in the broiler sector in Slovenia and their relationships

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Slovenia

Integrators collaborate with some actors, but otherwise they are on their own throughout the network from field to fork. They are also the strongest actors in the broiler sector.

There is a problem with unwillingness to share knowledge, especially in the case of competitors. On the other hand, participation in BIN can be time consuming. However, there is a great need for building a network between all Slovenian organisations/individuals working in broiler sector. All (potential) actors of BIN agree with the establishment of the broiler network and are happy to see something like this being started. There is currently no similar or existing network in the country.

Food retailers also play a very important role in the development of poultry meat produced under conditions standards going beyond the minimum legislation. In addition, their advertising can be very persuasive. Their presentation can quickly lead to misinterpretation. For this reason, it can cause problems for integrators, farmers, researchers, advisers and other actors. Perhaps the project and the creation of BINs will strengthen the connection between other actors and make them stronger and more resistant to retailers.

The cooperation between the strongest Slovenian intergrator and its cooperation partners, advisory service, research institute and associated breeders seems to be a (potentially) good partnership and cooperation. Includes (practical) knowledge and field practice.

The key actors to be involved in the project have been identified. However, we were cautious about who to invite to participate at BIN. It was difficult for us to find colleagues because there are few actors who are specifically involved in or experts on broiler farming.

Some of the actors are competitors of the existing participants. The integrators, for example, compete with each other. Problems to which the project is dedicated may not be of the greatest importance for them or (their) farmers. The main concern of farmers is profitability (prices, high costs of investments in innovations).

In addition, some actors would agree to participate, but the question is whether they would play an active role. Moreover, some would expect financial support for their participation in the project. Few actors are motivated because they are professionally involved in broiler production or its control.

The Slovenian members of the BIN agree with the strength of connections between actors. The network map provides a relatively good overview of the Broiler AKIS in the country. We reached out to organisations that we thought had knowledge and are willing to participate in the BroilerNet project. The participations who are engaged in the BIN are: Biotechnical Faculty of the University of Ljubljana, Perutnina Ptuj Group, Veterinary clinic of Perutnina Ptuj Group, Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia and the Poultry cooperative Ptuj and Association of Poultry Breeders who are in collaborative partnership.

3.11 Spain BroKIS

Introduction and country context

In Spain, the poultry industry contributes 13% to Spanish animal production. Broiler production represents the 81,7% of all the Spanish poultry production and the 17,2% of Spanish meat production. In 2020, Spain ranked in second place after Poland in poultry meat production with a share of 12.7% in the EU (27) production volume.

- 2020: 696.387.000 birds, 1.250.615 tons
- 2021: 680.711.000 birds, 1.331.407 tons

In Catalonia, broiler meat production in 2021 was 268.718 tons, which represents 20,5% of Spain's total meat production.

It is remarkable the importance of pig production both in Spain and, even more, in Catalonia where it represents 80% of all the meat produced.

There are two main types of broilers commercialized in Spain: yellow and white, depending on skin and fat colour. They are sold in different parts of the country depending on local preferences, although the big distribution companies are imposing the white ones.

Slow-growing broilers could be 5-8% of the total and it is believed to have reached its limits, due to the higher price in the market.

Regarding organic chicken, 511.879 birds were certified in Spain, less than 0,08% of the total.

Household consumption of fresh chicken meat represents 38% by weight and 27% by value of all fresh meat, being the most consumed.

The per capita consumption was 12,06 kg in 2021, but 13,65 kg in 2020. Although the data for these years must be considered with caution given the pandemic restrictions and therefore a drop in consumption in restaurants, schools, etc., there is a tendency towards a decrease in the consumption of all meats, including chicken but this shows the lower decrease.

The structure of the chicken meat production is totally vertically integrated. Almost all broiler production in Spain is integrated. There is great diversity between the sizes and steps of the chain that the integrators control. The simplest integrations have only farms to rear broilers. On the contrary, the biggest ones have broiler breeder farms, hatcheries, broiler farms, feed factories, slaughterhouses, and even in some cases retail sales.

Large integration companies have a national scope, while medium and small-sized ones have a regional scope. There is a progressive concentration of the production.

This fact entails:

- Great professionalization of the poultry farmer
- Great uniformity in production systems. Integration companies provide rules, technical assistance and control in handling, food, health, welfare, etc.
- Farmers are not the core of the system, but the integration companies.

From the group of large integrators, Vall Companys, which has recently acquired Sada, together with Guissona and Padesa, are based in Catalonia.

Figure 24. Percentage (%) in the chicken meat market

Overview and analysis of the Spanish BroKIS

Almost all broiler production is vertically integrated. Broiler production out of the integration system is only anecdotal.

Figure 25 present the network map of the Spanish Broiler sector. Key features are:

- The largest integrator companies carry out a large part of the production process, from breeding farms to the slaughterhouse.
- There is a large number of medium and small integrative companies that, in addition to broiler farms, offer different parts of the chain.
- The scope of large companies is all the country, while small and medium ones tend to have a regional scope.
- There is a progressive concentration of production.

Figure 25. Actors in the broiler sector in Spain and their relationships.

The relationship between integrator and integrated farmer is based in a contract. The integrator company must offer the animals for growing, the feed, the vet products, and technical and vet surveillance/advice. Farmers offer their farm facilities, including heating system, energy, water and litter and also its workforce. They must follow strictly the rules and procedures fixed by the integrator. The animals belong always to the integrator who decides when the growing period is over to slaughter the birds.

We consider these companies to be the core of the BroilerNet project in our country as they provide management, health, and welfare guides to poultry farmers.

The integrator companies are associated at regional level, mainly [FAC](#) in Catalonia and [ASAV](#) in the Valencian Community. FAC and ASAV include also egg production. The largest companies are also part of Avianza, a national representative association of the entire chain. FAC and ASAV are members of Avianza.

FAC is the association of the poultry production in Catalonia and represents its voice in front of the Catalan government, society, media and also in the national associations. It works closely with 3 other associations to represent the pork and poultry meat production, that is, over the 95% of the meat production in Catalonia. One of these associations is ASSOCAT which represents the poultry and rabbit slaughterhouses. In fact, the biggest

slaughterhouses belong to integrator companies, so they are also members of FAC. There are also a certain number of independent slaughterhouses, that sell the product in local markets and butchers.

Farmers are represented in professional organisations, usually in a regional level (Unió de Pagesos and JARC). These organizations are multi-sectoral, and poultry farmers have relatively little weight. They focus their work in the relationship between farmers and integrators.

[CESAC](#) is a poultry health laboratory that has the FAC and the integrator companies of Aragon as partners. It gives diagnostic services, support to the poultry farming and technical training to its partners. It also conducts the control of notifiable diseases for the administration. It is also a meeting point and promotes technical debate between the poultry veterinarians of the farms, where they share their knowledge. Veterinary companies also have it as a reference. It has great prestige throughout the Spanish poultry sector.

[CECAV](#) plays a similar role as CESAC in the Valencian Community.

As we have said, [Avianza](#) represents the poultry meat production in Spain. It works to promote and defend the image of the poultry sector, including turkeys and quails. It is also working to expand the market for our products outside the EU. Avianza is member of [AVEC](#) (Association of Poultry Processors and the Poultry Trade in the EU Countries).

In research, these are the main actors:

Research institutes: [IRTA](#) (Institut de Recerca i Tecnologia Agroalimentària) and [NEIKER](#) (Instituto Vasco de Investigación y Desarrollo Agrario). IRTA is the agrifood research and technology Institute of Catalonia and has research groups focused on poultry health and welfare. NEIKER is its basque counterpart and has also research groups relevant on poultry welfare and health.

[AECA - WPSA](#) (Asociación Española de Ciencia Avícola- World Poultry Association)

There is a large number of veterinary schools in Spain, but only few of them are doing research activities on poultry. The veterinary schools of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, the Universidad Cardenal Herrera in Valencia and the Universidad de Zaragoza, are the main ones.

[Selecciones Avícolas](#) and [Avinews](#) are the main media of the Spanish poultry sector.

The big integrators are the suppliers of meat chicken to the main supermarket chains. Local shops and market are provided by independent slaughterhouses and/or small integrators.

There are some NGO that have recently put the focus in some chains blaming them to offer the consumer meat chicken from farms that don't accomplish welfare rules. That means an additional pressure to the integrator. They have also influence in media and legislators.

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Spain

- The focus of BroilerNet actions are the integrator companies. Vets and technical personnel from these companies know closely their associated farmers and farms and how they work. They can provide a proper global analysis of their challenges for the next years. At the same time, when they would know the best practices in
- BroilerNet, they could adapt them to their own conditions and spread them among their farmers.
- The great and increasing level of concentration allows to work with a relatively few actors.
- As for the methods, the way to produce is very similar among all the companies, the problems and challenges are also common.
- CESAC is an important actor in the map due to its good reputation, big influence and organisation. It has a technical committee that gather the vets and technicians of poultry meat producers. It can provide valuable information on the health status of the poultry farms in Catalonia and Aragon.
- FAC has a close relationship with CESAC.
- IRTA has common projects with CESAC and participates in the former committee.
- IRTA has a big experience in European projects and has researchers specialized in the 3 areas of work and they have also worked in the poultry sector.
- Avianza as a national interprofessional organisation is not focused on farms, but in the final product. It could help in the dissemination of project's results but not in the process of searching and discussing the challenges and to find best practices.

3.12 Sweden BroKIS

Introduction and country context

In 2022 the Swedish broiler sector there are 150 producers, 99 % of these are conventional producers and less than 1 % organic producer. No free-range production is conducted in the country and just a small number of producers have other types of niche-production concepts. The broiler production is very much located in the southern parts of Sweden, due to the location of the abattoirs, hatcheries, and feed mills. Of the total meat consumption in Sweden, about 25 % consists of poultry meat. The self-sufficiency is 75 % of the consumed meat and the other quarter is imported

poultry meat. A majority of the production is part of the Swedish Poultry Meat Association (SPMA), which is a member organization that covers the whole production chain of Swedish broiler and turkey production (Figure 26). The Swedish Poultry Meat Association (SPMA) represents 99% of the poultry meat production in Sweden.

Figure 26. The organisation of the Swedish Poultry Meat Association that covers 99 % of the Swedish poultry meat production.

The members are obliged to participate in the animal health programs administered by SPMA such as:

- Foot pad lesion control
- Salmonella control
- Campylobacter control
- Coccidiosis and clostridiosis controls
- The animal welfare classification program
- Use of only approved feedstuff (no GMO, no fishmeal and only certified soy (ProTerra & RTRS))
- Antibiotic resistance policy

The Swedish animal welfare legislation differs from the EU-legislation and allows a maximum stocking density of 36 kg/m² with mandatory participation in the SPMA animal welfare classification program and foot pad lesion control.

Sweden has achieved efficient control of Salmonella, despite the industrialization of animal production. Due to this control, both red and white meat produced in Sweden is today virtually free of Salmonella. The objective of the Salmonella control is that animal products delivered for human consumption shall be free from Salmonella.

There is very limited use of antibiotics and there is also a system in place requiring that any use of antibiotics must be documented and reported yearly to the National Veterinary Institute, the authority in Sweden responsible for the national monitoring program covering antibiotic use and resistance patterns in Swedish animals. The number of Swedish flocks treated with antibiotics has for several years been below 1 %.

SPMA also works with industry related political issues, responds to legislative regulations, initiates research, contact with local communities, provides information about Swedish poultry meat production and are a firmly established quality brand among Swedish consumers. Competence within production advisory and veterinary medicine is mainly provided within the SPMA-organization and its members, apart from a few free-lance veterinarians who are contracted by the farmers.

Overview and analysis of the Swedish BroKIS

As presented in the introduction, 99 % of the Swedish broiler production is part of the SPMA organization. Affiliated companies (members) are Kronfågel AB, Guldfågeln AB, Atria, Knäreds Kyckling AB, Bjärefågel i Torekow AB, Ingelsta Kalkon AB, Blenta AB, Adelsåsen Produktion AB, SweHatch AB, SweChick AB/Aviagen, Svenska Foder, Lantmännen, Swedish Agro and approximately 150 Swedish poultry farmers.

The SPMA works as a hub for communication and collaboration within the industry. Advisors and veterinarians are working for the companies within SPMA. All members deliver production- and animal welfare data to a production database called TUPPEN. SPMA is coordinating TUPPEN.

Approximately 100 of the 150 farmers within the organisation are broiler farmers (remaining 50 are turkey farmers or rearing parent flocks). The farmers are located in the south of Sweden (see map in figure 2.) and have contracts with abattoirs in their close proximity. Around 95 % of the farmers in SPMA have conventional production according to Swedish legislation and less than 5% have other types of niche-production, such as slow growing hybrids and lower stocking density. No organic farmers are members of SPMA, and the organic production represents less than 1 % of the total production in Sweden. The size of the farms varies from large sites of more than 10 000 m² to small broiler houses of 500 m². The majority of the broiler houses are modern of high standard and insulated due to the northern climate.

Kronfågel is the largest poultry meat producing company in Sweden, slaughtering roughly 50 % of the total number of animals in the country. Kronfågel is part of the national company Scandi Standard.

They have one abattoir and production site and are the only one using gas

as stunning method. Kronfågel have contracted farmers that delivers conventional chickens to their abattoir but are also producing some organic chickens under the brand Bosarp´s chicken (not part of SPMA).

Guldfågeln is the second biggest producer of poultry meat in Sweden. It is a family-owned company and part of the larger company Blentagruppen. Guldfågeln has two larger abattoirs located one each coast of Sweden, a smaller production site in the south of Sweden and one abattoir for turkeys. Guldfågeln mainly have conventional broilers delivered to the company but also have a small production of a niche- concept called Solbacka. Solbacka production are using slow growing hybrids, lower stocking density and environmental enrichment.

Atria is an international company and has one abattoir in the south of Sweden. They produce poultry meat under the brand Lagerbergs Kyckling.

Knäred Kyckling AB is a small scale, family-owned integrator located on the western side of south Sweden.

Bjärefågel i Torekow AB is a small-scale family-owned integrator producing a niche-concept. They are located on the west coast of south Sweden and have main focus on slow growing hybrids and lower stocking density.

SweHatch AB is part of Scandi Standard (owner of Kronfågel) and have two hatcheries and several parent stock sites. The mainly hatch Ross 308, but also have a small production of slow growing hybrids.

Blenta is part of the larger family company Blentagruppen and has one hatchery and several parent stock sites. They hatch Ross 308.

SweChick is part of the global company Aviagen and provides the Swedish market with Grand Parent flocks. SweChick has one hatchery where they hatch the parents to Ross 308 and delivers to SweHatch and Blenta. SweChick is also big in export of parent stock.

The three feed companies Lantmännen, Svenska Foder and Swedish Agro provides feed to all the broiler farmers. The feed companies are also members in SPMA and are located in the southern parts of Sweden.

The Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), The Research Institute of Sweden (RISE) and The National Veterinary Institute (SVA) are the main actors within poultry research in Sweden. SPMA are partners in several research projects with these actors. The individual companies are also initiating projects and collaborating with these actors.

The governmental authorities involved in poultry production in Sweden are the Swedish Board of Agriculture, the Swedish Food Agency and the County Administrative Boards. SPMA have continuous contact with the

agencies and are participating in several different working groups on governmental level.

Figure 27. Actors in the broiler sector in Sweden and their relationships.

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in Sweden

Since SPMA is a central hub for most of the Swedish broiler industry, the formation of the BIN will be fairly easy. There are already a number of existing working groups within the areas of sustainability, animal welfare and animal health from which members of the BIN can be recruited. Since the industry is small, the actors presented in BroKIS map are all of interest to involve in the Broilernet project. From a farmer perspective it would be preferable to include a mix of small scale and larger scale farmers. Advisors and veterinarians can be recruited from the slaughter companies and researchers from existing collaborations with the actors presented in the BroKIS map. It would also be of interest to include actors from the hatcheries and feed companies. Although the focus of the project is on farm level, the whole production chain is connected and the knowledge of persons working in other positions could be valuable.

Engagement will probably be relying on the BNF's ability of project management and the BIN actors time schedules. This can be solved by well-prepared instructions, time schedules and the use of digital meeting tools as a compliment to physical meetings.

3.13 United Kingdom BroKIS

Introduction and country context

Chicken is the UK's most popular animal protein - with around 1 billion chickens slaughtered each year, with an average liveweight of 2.2 kg at point of slaughter producing approximately 1.7 metric tons of meat - it accounts for nearly half of all meat consumed. In 2021 UK poultry and poultry meat production was worth an estimated £2.9 billion.

The UK is around 65% self-sufficient in poultry meat. However, carcase balance is an issue as UK consumers prefer white poultry meat, favouring cuts of meat such as the breast over dark meat and offal. The UK therefore imports 487,000 tons of (primarily) chicken breast meat and exports 409,000 tons of (mainly) chicken legs, wings and offal. In 2022, poultry meat exports and imports were valued at £17.6 million and £145 million, respectively. Exports went mainly to Ireland (20.3%), Netherlands (19.6%), France (9.5%), Ghana (5.3%), and Spain (4.7%). Imports came mainly from the Netherlands (38.2%), Poland (35.2%), Germany (4.6%), Belgium (4.2%) and France (3.9%)⁴⁰.

The main broiler production systems in the UK include (i) standard indoor (approx. 85% of production, and approx. 10% reared to 30kg/m²), (ii) free range (approx. 3.5% of production), and (iii) organic (approx. 1% of production). The UK market for slow-growing breeds is currently a small portion of all broiler production (around 11%), but this may increase depending on uptake of the 'Better Chicken Commitment'⁴¹ which urges the adoption of additional standards for chicken production by 2026, including the use of breeds that demonstrate higher welfare outcomes (i.e. slower-growing breeds).

There have been over 170 confirmed cases of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) H5N1 in the UK since October 2022, posing significant challenges to the industry alongside increasing input costs and energy prices.

Overview and analysis of the UK BroKIS

The majority of the UK's broiler meat is produced by five major companies including Avara Foods (a joint venture between Faccenda and Cargill, established in 2018), Moy Park, 2 Sisters Food Group, Cranswick and Banham Poultry, all of which are privately owned. They operate integrated supply chains and own or partner with farms across the UK - there are more than 2,600 companies raising poultry of various scales.

⁴⁰ <https://oec.world/en/profile/bilateral-product/poultry-meat/reporter/gbr?redirect=true>

⁴¹ <https://www.nfuonline.com/archive?treeid=139718>

As shown in the Figure 28, the broiler supply chain 'stages' are breeding, hatching, and grow out farms, followed by slaughter and processing for wholesale and retail. There is a flow of inputs, products and services at various stages, for example catching teams and transport between each stage, feed and equipment, information and advice. There are also a range of external influences/pressures with regards to animal welfare, environmental standards, and food quality from government, NGOs and certification bodies, each of which have different roles and relationships, usually interfacing with producers and organisations

Figure 28. Actors in the broiler sector in the UK and their relationships.

In the UK, there is variable integration – although there are some large-scale integrators, there are also smaller scale businesses and independents, all of which could offer useful insights for the BIN.

Although most broilers are produced conventionally, involving growers using free range, and organic systems in the BIN would provide heterogeneity which could provide valuable exchange of knowledge and innovation stemming from adapting a practice used in one production system for another type of production.

Information and advice and input suppliers also need to develop and disseminate environmental, health and welfare solutions. Involving these actors in the BIN could allow for two-way exchange and co-design, strengthening developments going forward. Producer organisations help bridge the divide between societal pressure and policies and producers, striving to make social ideals practical at the farm/industry levels.

BIN formation will rely on tapping into existing networks and connections, for example using British Poultry Council Members and existing contacts (AB Agri and an Independent Veterinarian) as 'gatekeepers' to promote the BIN within their own networks. We will also attempt to connect with integrators, processors, retailer groups, and independents.

Implications for the formation of Broiler Net Innovation Network in The Netherlands

We plan to invite to the network:

- Farmers (growers) from different geographical locations and representing different scales and types of production systems. Farmers will be the main group in the BIN.
- Representatives of Hatcheries (to include breeding)
- Members of catching teams
- Representatives of input supply companies (pharmaceuticals, equipment, feed)
- Representatives of producer organisations
- Persons providing information and advice – veterinarians, consultants.
- Persons involved in R&D – agritech, universities, company representatives.

It may also be interesting to involve representatives from certification bodies, policy makers, integrators and buyers at specific points. However, to encourage collaborative working and sharing the BIN will consist mainly of those who work on or have regular contact with poultry growers. Other actors might be invited if the BIN expresses an interest in engaging with those actors, or request expertise that those actors could provide in a one-off setting.

4. Conclusion and way forward

The network mapping exercise provided valuable insight into the broiler sectors in the project countries and support the facilitators in their decision making on who to include in the BINs. Although there are clear similarities across the sector as in many countries there is a high level of integration, clear differences between countries can also be seen.

The BINs are networks of broiler producers together with relevant sector actors such integrator companies, advisors, researchers and veterinarians to enhance national collaboration, enable information exchange, and collect innovative ideas and good practices. The composition of these networks will vary depending on the structure of the BroKIS in each country as presented in this deliverable report. Furthermore, the composition will vary in each country based on the role of the facilitator's organisation in the sector, their connectivity and/or proximity with/in the sector and the facilitators capacity to mobilise relevant actors. Moreover, the composition of the BIN might vary over the years based on the challenges discussed.

The tasks (T1.1) related to this deliverable report was first and foremost for the BroilerNet innovation network facilitators to get a thorough understanding of the sector in their country and inform the decision making on who to include in the BINs. As the maps would provide interesting insight for the sector as a whole, the idea was to share these maps online through the website. Where possible these complex network maps were 'translated' and simplified and made available on the BroilerNet website <https://broilernet.eu/news/national-bins/>.

During the facilitators training in Paris (8 to 10 February 2023) the facilitators shared their maps and implications for network formation in each country discussed. Furthermore, the facilitators discussed anticipated challenges in mobilisation of the actor to participate in the BINs and how to manage these challenges. Based on the mapping exercise and the discussions during the training the facilitators will mobilise the relevant actors in their country to organise the first BIN meeting between March and May 2023

Discussions during the facilitator training on BIN formation and mobilisation.

